

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RIZK****FIRST NAME: Rana****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: PERIOD

This response paper intends to analyze the study material of the first period: *ACA-401D COURSEPACK*.

1) INTRODUCTION

An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1). It is a combination of one's personal knowledge and data collection set in an organized and understandable way. While writing an academic essay it is important to be structured, organized and transparent, thus writers are supposed to follow certain rules of style and cite their referenced statements in a clear way.

In order to write an essay, a writer follows a standard format based on a style guide. This style guide defines a systematic method of argumentation that will lead to prove the highlighted hypothesis, it improves the communication of ideas. One of the major components of a style guide is the citation of another researcher's information used in an essay.

In this paper I will discuss key factors to a successful academic essay. I will start by discussing the importance of using a style guide for the essay writing then elaborate about the importance of citations for transparency matters and avoiding plagiarism. My examples will be based on the American English, and the Chicago style of writing for I will be using it during the writing of my essays in this program.

2) USE OF A STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a technical tool used to ensure the consistency of the academic paper specially when it is written by more than one contributing author. A uniformed style, can help the author of an academic essay, choose the adequate vocabulary and terminology, use the necessary grammar and spelling, the correct font, abbreviation, symbols, bibliography listing and many other details. Such details are capable of giving the essay a better, organized and structured format; a common and easy to access essay.

For English academic essays, it is important to choose between the American or British English in order to define the style of the essay. Each cited style has its own sociolectic value and specific style guide. Of the main differences one can find between these two styles, I cite the pronunciation, the spelling, the meaning of the word, the punctuation, and the ways of writing and referencing. Therefore, authors willing to use the American English can use style guide such as *The Chicago Manual of Style* (Turabian 2013); for the authors using the British English in their essays, *The Cambridge Handbook for Editors, Authors and Publishers* Judith Butcher can be a useful reference.

As an example, in the Chicago style use, there is important rules to follow, such as the use of abbreviations is restricted to the parentheses, italic and quotation marks are used to emphasis on certain words in the essay. As for the essay format, margins are defined to be at least one inch on all the page edges, with the font twelve-point type, Times Roman, and indents to be one-half inch. The Chicago Manual also direct the writer on other criteria of the page numbering, headings and list, tables, footnotes and other.

A style guide helps also being transparent and not only consistent and structured. Following a certain style guide will allow the author to properly cite his references which serves to empower his essay.

3) CITATION

In order to write a convenient academic essay, an author has to define a hypothesis, and search for useful data to prove it. The data collected, should be able to answer his questions and convince the reader of his argument. One rule of thumb in an academic essay is the citation of the main owner of the information used. This citation method should be based on a certain format available in the style guide used by the author. This style will serve to emphasis on the information taken from another source, usually the original one.

As for the citations in the Chicago guide, there is two type of citations, in-text citation, and the list of work cited. The in-text citation method refers to citing a certain information within the essay. The name of the researcher who gave the information along with the page where it exists should be stated at the end of the sentence between parenthesis. The list of work cited, is the bibliography present in the end of the essay, it includes details of the source of information taken such as: the author name, date, book title, place of publication and publisher.

Citations has many benefits to the academic essays. It adds transparency to the discussed topic, and re-inforce the argument stated by the author when it shows other researches made and efforts done by another author on the same topic, with the same point of view. It also serves to give more information for the reader, and accessibility to other studies made by other authors; this can serve the next researcher to track the information and make advanced studies on a certain subject without omitting any idea. But the most important point of the citation is that it avoids plagiarism.

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5). It is an ethical and fundamental mistake that should not be frequent in an academic essay. In order to avoid the accusation of plagiarism, an author should either paraphrase the information adequately, or properly cite the source of information according to the guide style used, in a clear and explicit way.

Citation formatting, and plagiarism detection are both now easily done through programs that can be found on internet and that can interfere with the word document. Zotero is a program that can be helpful for academic writer in the citation regard. A writer can choose the style of citation according to the format and writing style. As for the plagiarism, Grammarly can be of use for plagiarism detection in addition of other services offered, such as the spelling and grammar detection.

4) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic paper is putting a set of information in a conversant way to transform a hypothesis first approached into a given and a conclusion. The essay reflects on the authors personality and point of view, and is dedicated to add value to all the information available on a certain subject. This is why, in order to be approved by the readers, and convenient, it needs to be framed in a certain uniformed style to make it organized and transparent.

An important detail when following a unified guide is properly citing the sources of data collected and information gathered. In-text and list of work cited, not only serve to be transparent, and avoid plagiarism, but to also permit the reader to keep track on the offered information and cover all the aspects in case of need of a further, more detailed knowledge.

This session was very useful to me, in order to understand how to shape my ideas, and standardize my way of writing. As for the assignments I will be sending during my study process, I will use the American English, and by that, the Chicago Style Guide. As for the citation, I will be using Zotero to help me cite properly.

REFERENCES

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- Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

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